

Impact of Strategic Environment Development on Control of Defense Industry Technology by Pt Pindad (Persero)

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ABSTRACT: *The development trend of the strategic environment is currently changing and predictable and has placed the future development of the world and the region full of uncertainty. The nature of dependence between countries and nations will be even greater, the distance between regions and countries, is no longer a barrier to interacting with each other. In the future, the threat has become increasingly real that will clash with the interests of groups or groups in the global region, to master technology in areas that are very much needed. The research method used is qualitative using a literature study approach. After analyzing that the results of this study concluded that the environmental impact of the strategy made PT Pindad (Persero) to make a breakthrough in the manufacture of weapons to support the mastery of technology. Responding to the problems above, and regarding the need for the main tools of the domestic defense system, PT Pindad (Persero) which is one of the defense strategy industrial companies owned by Indonesia is expected to become the main provider of defense and security tools for the TNI.*

KEYWORDS—Strategic Environment Development—Mastery of Technology, PT Pindad

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's position in viewing the development of the strategic environment at the world, regional and national levels which is increasingly moving forward and complex, has raised military and military threats. Indonesia as the largest country in the Southeast Asia region has many sources of strength such as population, geographical conditions, natural resources to increase strength in the region. Laksmana (2011). In addition, with the condition of a very wide area and being Indonesia's responsibility, it shows the need to prepare a formidable defense force in order to maintain the sovereignty of one Indonesian territory. The development of weapons technology also has the potential to strengthen the defense system and state security. Today, Indonesia's national defense must not only be supported by strong and tough military personnel, but the national defense must also be supported by the sophistication of the technology of the main weapon system. RI Law number 03 of 2002 states that national defense is an effort to maintain territorial integrity, the sovereignty of the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from various threats and disturbances. The law describes the national defense system that involves all citizens, territories, and national resources.

This is carried out in a total, integrated, directed, and continuous manner to uphold state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the safety of the entire nation from all threats. With regard to threats, the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2019 concerning the Empowerment of National Resources defines as all efforts and activities both from within the country and from abroad that are contrary to Pancasila because it endangers the

existence of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia for the safety of the nation as a whole. PT Pindad (Persero) which is one of the strategic industrial companies in the defense sector owned by Indonesia, which is expected to be the main provider of weapons system tools for the TNI, as well as to support the defense and security of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia by carrying out integrated efforts in the field of defense and security equipment. and industrial equipment began to handle the production of weapons, ammunition, and combat vehicles. The questions that arise in this paper are (1) what is the impact of the development of the strategic environment on the mastery of weapons technology in Indonesia? (2) who has a role in the mastery of Indonesian weapons technology?

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses qualitative research methods, which according to Sugiyono (2019) says qualitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of postpositivism used to examine natural objects. Where this research is dominated by library research activities and field studies confirmed by the informant PT. Pindad (Persero). Creswell (2016) asserts that researchers in qualitative research will try to build meaning about a phenomenon based on views or opinions from various sources. Data analysis techniques used data triangulation techniques, as well as research locations visited by researchers, namely:

1. PT. Pindad (Persero), Jl. Terusan Gatot Subroto No.517, Kebon Kangkung, Kiaracondong, Sukapura, Kiaracondong, Bandung, West Java 40284
2. Library of the Indonesia Defense University, IPSC Sentul Area, Bogor, West Java 16810.
3. National Library of Indonesia, Jl. Salemba Raya No. 28A Jakarta Pusat 10430

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the development of the international strategic environment, Indonesia's position highlights changes in international relations after the end of the Cold War which affected the condition of national stability, this was stated in the 1995 Indonesian Defense White Paper (BPPI). . Meanwhile, in view of the development of the regional strategic environment, it gives priority to countries that are members of ASEAN. The concept of regional resilience in the Asean region has succeeded in maintaining regional balance, where the development of strong defense technology has contributed to modernization assistance from the point of view of military power. Mastery of military technology in the future will greatly assist the Indonesian National Army (TNI) in maximizing its main duties and functions in maintaining state sovereignty. The development of formidable defense technology will contribute to modernization in terms of military strength. Through the development of advanced technology in the future, it can add to the superiority of a nation in building military strength. In addition, the renewal is also intended for the Indonesian nation to be able to equalize its position with other countries in terms of mastery of defense technology. In line with this policy, the government has established a defense technology mastery program with an emphasis on seven superior programs for defense and security equipment.

A. Definition

a. Understanding Impact

The definition of impact is a strong influence that can have consequences, good or bad, according to the translation of the Big Indonesian Dictionary. Impact is divided into two meanings, namely: 1. Good impact, is a desire to influence, persuade, convince, or give an impression to others, with the intention that they follow or support a good desire. 2. Understanding bad effects, is a desire to seduce, convince, influence or give an impression to others, with the aim that they follow or support their bad desires and involve certain things.

b. Development of the global strategic environment

The current global world movement is characterized by a shift in the influence of the United States' power; especially in the Asia-Pacific region is gradually being crushed by the rapid growth in China. The United States certainly does not want inequality of influence; because with the loss of influence of power in the Asia-Pacific

region will bring the effect of enormous losses on all aspects of the life of the United States. The six-year period, from 2014 to 2020, is sufficient for China to catch up with the United States, at least to balance its power and influence in the Asia Pacific region. This of course puts the United States in a suspicious position, as well as countries in certain regions, especially those in direct conflict with China, who are currently developing war strategies. The United States plans to shift attention from the Middle East to Asia-Pacific by 2020 by placing about 60% of the Navy's strength in the Asia-Pacific region. The delivery of US warplanes to several countries in the Pacific Ocean, such as Thailand, India, Singapore and Australia, with the aim of strengthening the presence of US military forces in the Pacific Ocean. This situation must be prepared because Indonesia's position is in an inappropriate position because it has to choose between 2 (two) major powers, namely the United States and China.

a. Regional strategic environment development

Several strategic issues after the signing of the ASEAN cooperation agreement to strengthen cooperation in the fields of security, socio-culture and economy are a momentum to continue to prepare themselves so that in entering ASEAN free trade, the Indonesian nation has competitiveness.³¹ Even though politically ASEAN countries look more stable. However, due to pressure from developed countries and the enthusiasm to defend their country's interests, relations between ASEAN countries also create potential tensions. Indonesia-Australia bilateral relations experienced ups and downs, Australia's tendency to rely on alliances with the United States and its allies, wanted to control the region as a consequence of its position as deputy shierief in Asia Pacific by applying the "pre-emptive strikes doctrine and Australian Maritime Identification System (AMIS), " is a security zone 1,000 nautical miles from the coast of Australia to protect Australian shipping, ports and oil platforms. Meanwhile, the US also pays attention to this policy because the US has a big goal for the Malacca Strait area as the most densely populated shipping lane in the world. Therefore, Australian state policy can also be defined as efforts to internationalize the Malacca Strait region to secure the goals of western countries in this region.

b. Development of the national strategic environment

The most prominent development of the strategic environment at the national level is the emergence of various conflicts within the country, both vertical, horizontal and communal conflicts. This needs to be used as an indicator in studying the development of the strategic environment in the national scope. The development of the national strategic environment can be monitored by studying the conditions of all aspects of people's lives, both natural, such as aspects of Natural Resources, Geography, and Demographics, as well as dynamic/social aspects such as aspects of defense and security, ideology, politics, economy, social culture.

B. Impact of mastery of technology

a. Global Environmental Influence

Currently the security threat of war between countries is minimal, and international relations are still marked by uncertainty related to economic, political, and security issues. Non-war security threats have mostly been replaced by non-war security threats. At the international level, the strategic environment that is thought to have a dominant influence on Indonesia's defense policy in the context of mastering technology, among others:

- 1) Together with the Agency for the Assessment and Application of Technology (BPPT) and in collaboration with the Swedish SAAB, PT Pindad (Persero) held a national seminar entitled Achieving Air Defense Superiority Through the Latest Missile and Sensor Technology. Missile technology is one part of several priority programs in the development of mastery of defense and security industry technology, this is a decision of the Defense Industry Policy Committee (KKIP) meeting. With other products such as tanks, submarines, and fighter jets.
- 2) The impact of technological developments and the defense industry. The development of science and technology in the last period has caused changes in the military field called the Revolution in military affairs (RMA) and the defense system. So that the RMA will contribute to the development and change of doctrine, military organization, and war strategy. As a result of the RMA, it has caused an arms race between big

countries and created technological boundaries between developed or large countries against developing countries, such as Indonesia.

b. Regional Environmental Influence

Indonesia's strategic environment at the regional level, both in the Southeast Asia region in particular and the Asia-Pacific region in general, is characterized by developments and strategic tendencies in mastering technology, namely:

- 1) Support from the President of the Republic of Indonesia, Joko Widodo regarding the addition of production capabilities and the acceleration of PT Pindad's technological mastery which continues to be improved to meet the needs of the TNI more optimally. By pioneering the acceleration of mastery of technology through the Transfer of Technology process with several players in the global defense industry.
- 2) Regarding technology mastery, Pindad Management hopes that the products that have been produced can provide satisfaction to users and continue to build trust to continue using domestic products. Weapon products that have been made with the best quality. This has been proven in activities at the Australian Army of Skill Arms at Meeting (AASAM) for nine consecutive years in Australia, at the ASEAN Armies Rifle Meet (AARM) and the Brunei International Shooting Skill at Arms Meet (BISAM). compete with weapons made by foreign manufacturers.

c. National Environmental Influence

In the next few years, the influence of Indonesia's national strategic environment will still face complicated problems, including:

- 1) There is a problem of separatism, especially Papuans who want to try to get special treatment, and even want to separate themselves from the Republic of Indonesia.
- 2) Social conflicts caused by a combination of two or more factors, such as ethnic sentiments, religious sentiments, low tolerance between communities and the existence of economic disparities in society.
- 3) Terrorism in the country. There needs to be a good synergy in terms of weapons strength between the TNI and the Indonesian Police to overcome this. If this is not done, Indonesia will still be seen as a hotbed of terrorism in Southeast Asia.

For this reason, mastery of technology must be maximally targeted to overcome domestic national issues. Regarding mastery of technology, PT Pindad (Persero) introduced four new variants of their weapons to the public. The introduction of these new types of weapons was carried out at the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia (Kemenhan RI). This product is the responsibility of PT Pindad (Persero) to continue to provide the highest quality products to be used by users. The products are Assault Rifle/SS3, Assault Rifle/SS2 subsonic 5.56mm, PM3 submachine gun and G2 Premium Pistol. These weapons are the result of processed Pindad products obtained from serious and relentless Research and Development (RD) efforts, as well as from suggestions and inputs given by users.

This is a brief overview of the development of the strategic environment that we must be aware of and overcome together. Hope it is useful.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion from the results of the above discussion is that in relation to the influence of global, regional, and national strategic environmental developments that have an impact on the emergence of various threats, challenges and disturbances that may arise from within and outside the territory of the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia, the role of a formidable defense and security force is needed, in particular. the strength of the Indonesian National Army (TNI) as a role holder in national defense. In building this strength, it is hoped that efforts to master technology in the field of defense and security are expected. The existence of sophisticated supporting technology in the main weapon system is believed by many parties to be able to help the TNI to be able to carry out its duties in upholding the law of national sovereignty. In supporting the defense and security sector, solid cooperation between ministries/institutions is needed in realizing mastery of technology in order to

achieve an independent defense industry. The ministries/agencies are the ministry of defense as the leading sector, the Minister of SOEs, the Minister of Industry, the Minister of Research and Technology, the Minister of Finance.

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